

CASE STUDY

Impact of recyclability on the mechanical properties of coated plastic materials for the automotive and electronic sectors

[version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]

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V1 **First published:** 04 Mar 2024, 4:51
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16888.1>
Second version: 06 Feb 2025, 4:51
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16888.2>
Latest published: 31 Mar 2025, 4:51
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16888.3>

Abstract

This research focuses on the study of the mechanical properties (tensile and impact strength) of Acrylonitrile-Butadiene-Styrene (ABS) and its blends with Polycarbonate (ABS/PC) including recycled and painted material. A comprehensive assessment was done to determine the impact of reprocessing cycles, remaining coating and their combined effect in the final properties of the recycled polymer. Post-consumer materials are in an already-aged state, lowering their initial properties. Mechanical recycling methods showed that the reprocessing cycles have a higher impact on the mechanical performance than the amount of recycling material content. Also, the material is often coated when they are about to be recycled. The remaining coating impurities play a major role in the recycling process, losing up to 42% of the impact strength for ABS and 28% for ABS/PC. It was demonstrated that below a 10% of remaining paint, both materials retained its performance as a neat product. Impurities was declared to be the most pernicious element on the recycling process and their elimination must be a priority regarding this objective. These results provide a better knowledge of the recycling effect and can be used to decide the potential recyclability of plastic. The ascribed project of this study (DECOAT) aims to develop efficient systems to remove coatings at the end-of-life of the part, to reduce the damage and promote the use of recycled material in high-tech applications.

Open Peer Review

Approval Status

	1	2	3
version 3 (revision) 31 Mar 2025			
version 2 (revision) 06 Feb 2025		 view	
version 1 04 Mar 2024	 view		

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Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

Keywords

Recyclability, plastic, coating, automotive, electronic, tensile strength, impact strength, ABS, PC, reprocessing, mechanical performance, end-of-life

This article is included in the [Materials Engineering gateway](#).

This article is included in the [Horizon 2020 gateway](#).

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Author roles: **Ventosinos Louzao V:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Writing – Original Draft Preparation; **García Murias D:** Conceptualization, Project Administration, Writing – Review & Editing; **De Dios Álvarez MÁ:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing; **Acuña Domínguez PA:** Methodology, Validation, Writing – Original Draft Preparation; **Paredes Barros E:** Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Ledo Bañobre R:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing

Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information: This study has been funded by the project “DECOAT” (Recycling of coated and painted textile and plastic materials). DECOAT is funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program under Grant Agreement n° 814505. For more information about the project, please visit www.decoat.eu.

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

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How to cite this article: Ventosinos Louzao V, García Murias D, De Dios Álvarez MÁ *et al.* **Impact of recyclability on the mechanical properties of coated plastic materials for the automotive and electronic sectors [version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]** Open Research Europe 2024, 4:51 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16888.1>

First published: 04 Mar 2024, 4:51 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16888.1>

Introduction

Plastics are one of the most relevant materials worldwide due to their unique combination of properties, including chemical resistance, ease of processing, low cost and lightweight potential. These properties allow them to be used in a variety of key components for different sectors, such as construction, architecture, cushioning, electronics or the aeronautical and automotive. On top of that, the increasing use of plastic materials increases the post-consumer plastic waste produced, giving concern about their management and recyclability techniques. According to a new report of the OECD organization, only about 9% of collected plastic waste is recycled while 22% is mismanaged globally. Although, recent improvements on the reusability and recyclability of plastics had been performed, the global production of plastics from recycled or secondary plastics has more than quadrupled in the last 20 years, but this is still only 6% of the size of total plastics production, being most of the plastics in use today virgin or primary plastics, made from crude oil or gas¹.

The automotive and electronic industries manufacture key products for the current market needs. They use high amounts of plastic materials, including Polypropylene (PP), Polyurethane (PU), Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC), Acrylonitrile-Butadiene-Styrene (ABS), Polycarbonate (PC) and many others. These sectors fulfil the demand of around a 15 % of the Europe demand for plastics materials². Among them, ABS and PC are one of the most important ones. ABS is a polymeric material that stands out for being highly resistant to impact and chemical corrosion along with a low melting point that allows an easy processability. It is widely used automotive and electronics as an impact modifier or integral part of dashboards and steering wheel covers. However, ABS has lower mechanical properties than most of the engineering plastics on the market³. PC on the other hand, is a widely used amorphous plastic which has some outstanding characteristics like transparency or high impact strength but possesses poor solvent resistance and harder processability due to its high viscosity⁴. Combining those materials in a ABS/PC blend, increases the thermomechanical resistance of ABS^{5,6} and reduces the cost and increases the processability of PC³. ABS/PC blends are commonly applied in automotive parts as well as housings of electronics and household appliances⁷. However, it was reported that even 1 wt.% of a polymeric impurity when added to virgin ABS causes unacceptable reductions in impact strength and ductility⁸. Such a challenge is of industrial importance and could lead to massive improvement in the use of recyclable materials in the automotive and electronic sectors.

Commonly, plastic components are employed in visible applications, where design plays an important factor in the consumer's decision and for that, they are commonly coated with paints or varnishes that improve their appearance and their resistance to external agents. Coatings are an additional stone on the recyclability path, as they are designed to be strongly attached to the substrate surface and resist aggressive conditions^{9,10}. To allow its reuse, the coating must be separated from the component, adding an additional cost than just a mere mechanical recycling. However, it is very hard to eliminate all

the coating impurities before the recycling process. Several studies showed that impurities decrease the mechanical properties of the recycled material, preventing its use on demanding applications¹¹⁻¹⁴. For that reason, the highly technological sectors, such as the automotive industry, have been reluctant to use large amounts of recycled plastic, fearing a significant reduction of the material performance and thus, making, painted parts virtually not recyclable. Besides impurities, several factors can still affect the final properties of the recycled materials. The ageing of the material at the end-of-life, the number of reprocessing cycles or the amount of recycled material can all negatively impact the performances of the material^{10,12,15-18}.

In the present study, a comprehensive assessment was done to evaluate the effect of each of those factors (ageing, reprocessing cycles and coating impurities) and a cross-combination of those which showed higher impact, to provide an insight about the factors influencing the performance of a recyclable material. The results provide a better knowledge of the recycling effect and can be used to decide the potential applications of recycled plastic. The ascribed project (DECOAT) aims to develop efficient systems to remove coatings at the end-of-life of the part, to reduce the damage and promote the use of recycled material in high-tech applications.

Methods

The assessment was done for 2 industrial use-cases:

- **Automotive use-case:** A rear door garnish made of ABS coated with a solvent-based primer, a black paint and a clear coat provided by Maier S. Coop (Gernika, Spain).
- **Electronic use-case:** A socket part made of ABS/PC coated with a water-based anthracite paint provided by Panasonic (Istanbul, Turkey).

To perform the present study, the mentioned polymers were ABS Elix H605 Black (Elix polymers, Tarragona Spain) and ABS/PC Lupoy HT5007A White (LG Chem, South Korea). They were molded using an injection molding machine Engel Victory 350Tn (ENGEL, Austria), to obtain 3 kinds of samples according to the testing needs: Tensile strength (ISO-527-2 type A), impact strength (ISO-179-2) and plates of 110x160x3 mm. Average value and standard deviation of 5 samples were reported. When required, the samples were coated with their corresponding paint, according to the supplier.

The study was divided into two different methods, focusing on the impact of the ageing, reprocessing cycles, recycle content and amount of coating impurities on the properties of the case materials.

1.1. Method to assess the properties of the material at the end-of-life: Effect of the ageing

In a real-life scenario, the parts presumed to be recycled are already damaged due to the exposure to different environmental conditions (temperature, moisture, sun irradiation, etc.) during several years along its lifetime. For that reason, the material is

already in an aged state before the start of the recycling process. Commonly, an aged material has presumably lower mechanical properties than the pristine one^{15,16}. To evaluate this loss of properties, ABS and ABS/PC samples were exposed to accelerated ageing tests (Figure 1), following the standard of the automotive and the electronic sector, respectively. After the ageing, the samples were tested to determine the tensile and the impact strength of the material, respectively. The use cases are depicted below:

- **For the automotive use-case**, DIN 75220 standard for exterior parts was followed, outlining the process of simulating prolonged solar radiation exposure. The tests consist of alternating 10 dry cycles (including irradiation) with 5 humid cycles, for a total of 15 days of accelerated ageing. The exposure was done in a climatic chamber FITOTERM 14.000 (Figure 1A).
- **For the electronic use-case**, samples were exposed to 70°C during 168 h in an oven (Figure 1B), following an internal standard from Panasonic.

1.2. Method to determine the effect of the recycling process on plastic material

During the recycling process of coated parts proposed in this study, we identified different factors that can affect the properties of the material. Table 1 summarizes the parameters tested for each factor. For each factor, tensile and impact strength were reported.

▪ The mechanical recycling process itself:

The recycling process consists of several steps of reprocessing. First, the material parts are transformed into shredded material. Then, they are mixed with virgin one at different proportions according to the desired recycled content (15, 30, 50 and 100%). Last, the material is injected to prepare the test samples according to the standards. Following this procedure, the pressure, shear, and temperature during the reprocessing can shorten the polymeric chain, affecting the mechanical properties^{8,9}. Since a circular approach is aimed, we evaluated the properties after five reprocessing cycles and different recycled contents (Figure 2).

▪ The remaining coating impurities:

Most of the recycling procedures are not perfectly efficient, therefore some coating impurities can remain in the plastic

substrate, affecting its properties^{10,12}. To reproduce this situation, plastic pellets were coated and then mixed with virgin pellets, controlling the weight of coating that was introduced in the mixture (Figure 3). It was calculated that the automotive part (ABS) has 1,92 wt.% of coating and the electronic part (ABS/PC) has 0,40 wt.% respectively. Therefore, those proportions were considered as 100% of coating impurities, corresponding to an untreated part.

Figure 1. A) ABS samples into the climate chamber B) ABS/PC samples into the oven.

Figure 2. Experimental procedure to evaluate the mechanical recycling effect on the properties of plastic.

Figure 3. Experimental procedure to evaluate the effect of coating impurities.

Table 1. Design of experiment to evaluate the effect of the recycling process proposed in this study.

	FACTOR 1. Mechanical recycling	FACTOR 2. Coating impurities	FACTOR 3. Combination of factors
Purpose	To determine the recycled content and nº of cycles with the best compromise between environmental impact and material performance	To determine the maximum remaining coating content to guarantee the circularity and effectiveness	To determine the impact of both effects (impurities and reprocessing) on the recyclability of the material
Variables	- Recycled content (15%, 30%, 50%, 100%) - Nº of reprocessing cycles: 1 to 5	0.5%, 1%, 3%, 10%, 25%, 50% and 100% of remaining coating respect to a fully painted part.	- 5%, 10% and 20% of coating impurities - 1–5 reprocessing cycles

■ Combined effect of reprocessing and coating impurities:

Through the previous factors presented above, it was noted that the reprocessing of the material and the presence of coating impurities could have a big impact on the mechanical performance of the plastic product. For that reason, to study those combined effects, ABS and ABS/PC pellets were coated as in the process showed in Figure 3 (5, 10 and 20% of remaining coating impurities) and then subjected to a five-cycle reprocessing process. The aim of this analysis is to determine the possible synergistic effect between these recycling factors.

Results

Effect of the ageing on the mechanical properties of the material

Specimen samples were manufactured following the procedure explained in section 3 and then tested for tensile and impact strength. As shown in Table 2, Aged ABS showed a significant loss of properties on both tensile modulus and impact strength (Figure S1), decreasing 12.3% and 18.8% respectively in comparison to virgin ABS. On the other hand, aged ABS/PC was also damaged by such process, with a loss of properties of 4.9% and 17.0% for tensile modulus and impact strength, respectively (Figure S2) in comparison to pristine ABS/PC. ABS suffered a higher degradation on its properties than the ABS/PC blends. This is explained by the lower

UV radiation resistance of ABS due to the double bonds of the butadiene unit, whereas PC is relatively stable to the light¹⁹. Also, the higher tensile strength and T_g of PC, results on a higher resistance to thermal degradation than ABS, thus improving the overall properties in the blend. On top of that, it can be observed a higher damage on the impact resistance performance than in the tensile strength in both ABS and ABS/PC. This is due to surface degradation upon ageing, mostly on the polybutadiene phase of the polymer. Ageing leads to chain scission and cross-linking, that restricts the polymer chain mobility and decreases the free volume, resulting in an increase of the T_g upon ageing, whereas the effect on the styrene-acrylonitrile phase is less significant^{20,21}. It can be observed that automotive and electronic parts following an ageing process, suffer enough loss of mechanical properties. These results showed the importance of the ageing studies on automotive and electronic parts in the mechanical and life cycle analysis of these products.

1.3. Effect of the recycling and purification process on the mechanical properties

■ Assessment of the mechanical recycling effect

Samples were manufactured following the procedure explained in section 3.2 and then tested for tensile and impact strength. Average values of tensile strength are plotted in Figure 4 and Figure 5

Table 2. Tensile and impact strength results of test specimens after ageing tests.

Test samples	ABS-ref	ABS-After automotive ageing	ABS/PC-ref	ABS/PC-After electronic ageing
Tensile strength (Mpa)	2407.4 ± 84.8	2110.6 ± 131.4	2276.5 ± 159.7	2165.7 ± 118.0
Impact strength (KJ/m ²)	18.43 ± 0.25	14.97 ± 0.32	50.53 ± 2.00	41.93 ± 1.77

Figure 4. Effect of recycled content and reprocessing cycles on the tensile strength of ABS.

Figure 5. Effect of recycled content and reprocessing cycles on the tensile strength of ABS/PC.

for ABS and ABS/PC respectively. For recycled ABS, the tensile modulus remains very stable and close to the reference showed in Table 2 (1st cycle of 100 % recycled material), regardless of the recycled content nor the number of reprocessing cycles (Figure 4). These results showed the excellent behavior of ABS as a recyclable material for the automotive sector. Regarding ABS/PC for electronics, the effect of the recycling content and different injection cycles on the tensile strength showed a positive impact (Figure 5). Like ABS alone, the values of ABS/PC remain close to the reference one (Table 2). Notably, an initial increase (about 10%) of the tensile modulus with the introduction of increasing content of recycled material was observed. It was reported that changes in the orientation of the polymeric chains at the macromolecular scale could lead to bear increasing loadings during the test²². The reprocessing effect showed as well increasing values with a slightly higher impact than ABS alone. Degradation caused by several injections could produce a reduction in the mean distances and the length of the PC macromolecular chains, thus increasing the Van der Waals interactions and leading to an increasing tensile strength²³. Despite this, it is expected a reduction on the mechanical performance after more than 5 cycles due to the continuous degradative process²⁴.

Unlike the tensile strength, impact strength performance changes especially with each reprocessing cycle. Average values of Charpy impact strength are plotted in Figure 6 and Figure 7 for ABS and ABS/PC respectively. In both materials, the impact of increasing recyclable content is almost negligible, although

the presence of recyclable content decreases the performance in comparison to the reference Table 2. The impact strength dropped on average by 5.9% for ABS and 14.5% for ABS/PC when recycling content is introduced. On the other hand, the impact of the reprocessing cycles is of significance. The first cycle of each recycled content for ABS keeps similar strength as the reference (Table 2). However, after each additional cycle, the performance drops dramatically, decreasing up to 12.5% on average for the 5th cycle (Figure 6). In the case of ABS/PC, the loss of performance due to the reprocessing cycles is even more dramatic than in the ABS case. ABS/PC losses impact strength from the first reprocessing cycle and drops 23 % on average after 5 cycles (Figure 7). On the other hand, ABS/PC seems to show higher stability on the first two reprocessing cycles regardless of the recycling content but drops abruptly after the 3rd cycle. The loss of mechanical properties in ABS is often attributed to thermo-oxidative degradation in the polybutadiene phase only, whereas additional physical ageing can also occur in the styrene-acrylonitrile phase²⁵. The polymeric degradation of ABS is thermodynamically favorable after periods of exposure to heat and oxygen (such as after reprocessing), leading to a deterioration of the mechanical properties²⁶. Commonly, the introduction of PC leads to a higher stability upon reprocessing^{27,28}. However, it was reported that the decrement of strength with reprocessing might be attributed to the decrease of the molecular weight and chain scission. Broader chain length distribution and shorter chain induced poor chain entanglements, and consequently, the impact strength dropped with increasing reprocessing³.

Figure 6. Effect of recycled content and reprocessing cycles on the impact resistance of ABS.

Figure 7. Effect of recycled content and reprocessing cycles on the impact resistance of ABS/PC.

▪ Assessment of the coating impurities effect

Samples were manufactured following the procedure explained in section 3.2 (Figure 3) and then tested for tensile and impact strength. Results are showed in Table 3 and Figure S3 and S4. Regarding ABS, the tensile modulus decreases when coating impurities are present. For coating contents from 0.5 to 50%, the tensile modulus decreases 12% on average. With 100% of remaining coating, it decreases 16%. For ABS/PC, the effect of coating impurities on the tensile modulus is not clear, since there is a huge variability of data which is more evident with the higher impurity content. However, a slight decrease in the performance can be presumed. For the impact strength, again, a clear relationship was found between the amount of coating impurities and the performance of both ABS and ABS/PC. Both ABS and ABS/PC can retain its properties when the coating impurities fall below 3% compared to the neat material. However, with full coating (100% impurities) decreases the impact strength of ABS and ABS/PC by 42% and 28%, respectively. It can be thus noted the better performance of ABS/PC with respect to ABS.

According to the trend curves, it is enough with 14.2% and 21.2% of the remaining coating impurities to lost about the 10% of the performance of the reference ABS and ABS/PC, respectively. The presence of coating impurities had a very large impact on the mechanical properties. It was reported that these impurities usually have different dimensions and produce an inhomogeneous structure with weak mechanical points, which resulted in local cavitation and higher stress for the ABS matrix that allows an easy breakage^{7,13,29}. This result shows the importance of a good cleaning process before the start of a recycling procedure.

▪ Assessment of the combined effect of coating impurities and reprocessing cycles

Specimen samples were manufactured following the procedure explained in section 3.2 and then tested for tensile and impact strength. Results for ABS analysis are shown in Figure 8 and Figure 10 whereas for ABS/PC are shown in Figure 9 and Figure 11. The data for the tensile and impact strength of ABS

Table 3. Tensile and impact strength of ABS with varied coating impurities (%).

Material	Mechanical performance	Coating impurities (%)							
		Ref	0.5%	1.0%	3.0%	10.0%	25.0%	50.0%	100.0%
ABS	Tensile modulus (Mpa)-Avg	2407.4	2129.2	2120.0	2119.8	2155.6	2090.1	2147.1	2025.8
	Impact strenght (KJ/m ²)-Avg	18.43	17.98	18.53	18.38	17.60	14.73	13.13	10.70
ABS/PC	Tensile modulus (Mpa)-Avg	2276.5	2333.5	2119.5	2176.4	2171.9	2203.3	2191.0	2431.5
	Impact strenght (KJ/m ²)-Avg	50.53	49.22	49.08	51.11	46.09	44.87	41.26	36.49

Figure 8. Combined effect of reprocessing cycles and coating impurities on the tensile strength of ABS.

Figure 9. Combined effect of reprocessing cycles and coating impurities on the tensile strength of ABS/PC.

Figure 10. Combined effect of reprocessing cycles and coating impurities on the impact resistance of ABS.

Figure 11. Combined effect of reprocessing cycles and coating impurities on the impact resistance of ABS/PC.

showed a general drop on the properties of the material with increasing reprocessing cycles and coating impurities. ABS decreased on average 9% and 24% for the tensile and impact strength respectively. This result implies a higher effect on the impact than in the tensile strength. Nonetheless, the combined factors showed no synergistic effect, being the effect of the coating individually, the one with probably higher contribution. In the case of ABS/PC, the performance decreased on average by 3.0% and 15% for the tensile and impact strength respectively. ABS/PC retained notably its properties in comparison to ABS. In the same way as ABS, no synergistic effect was found. One possibility to explain this lack of synergistic degradative effects could be on the impurities size and distribution. As the materials are reprocessed, the impurities could be distributed homogeneously due to the temperature and shear stress of the process, thus reducing its size. As the impurities size diminishes, the local stress increases due to the interaction between the polymer molecules, leading to a reduced effect of the coating impurities on the impact strength decrease²⁹.

Conclusion

A comprehensive assessment of the mechanical properties of recycled materials was done during this, isolating different factors that can potentially damage the polymers and therefore, limit their application in high-tech sectors such as automotive and electronic industries. Through ageing tests, it was demonstrated that a part to be recycled is already damaged by years of environmental exposure. Therefore, the recycling process should have almost no impact to avoid even more degradation.

- Mechanical recycling showed that ABS and ABS/PC are stable after the first reprocessing cycle, regardless of the recycled content, but a loss of properties is reported after 2 cycles or more, affecting mostly the impact strength.
- In coated parts, the coating impurities were proved to be very pernicious in terms of mechanical properties, especially for the impact strength. These impurities must be eliminated allowing only almost <10 % impurities to retain the mechanical performance.
- The analysis for the combination of both previous factors showed no synergistic effect between the degradative processes. Impact strength was the one with a high depletion on its performance.

From this study, it is encouraged the importance of a high-performance cleaning process that avoids the presence of coating impurities in the recyclable material in order to ensure the use of recyclable products into high-end industries like automotive and electronics.

Data availability

The raw data cannot be made public since it is within the non-disclosure agreement (NDA) signed by the Consortium. The reader should apply for individual access to the data directly with vanesa.ventosinos@ctag.com.

Data are available for readers under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license \(CC-BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

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Current Peer Review Status: ? ?

Version 1

Reviewer Report 14 August 2024

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.18250.r39863>

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The work for review presents a clear and interesting approach to the global issue of waste accumulation by focusing on ABS, PC, and blends in the forms of virgin and post-consumer materials. The authors discussed the degradation of the plastic component may experience during its service life which more often results in a deterioration of results.

There are some grammar issues found throughout the paper but nothing too impactful that the paper's message is lost. Please ensure to give another read-through.

Please note, that the bolded numbered parts must be addressed for the article to be scientifically sound (as required by the reviewer form).

--Introduction --

The introduction was written clearly and with good flow.

- 1. I would suggest adding a line for the specific production/waste or collection rate for ABS and PC plastics to strengthen why these two materials should be of focus.**
2. Polymer names are common nouns, and as such should not need to be capitalized, please finish on page 3 second paragraph. The capitalization may be just for the acronym but it is still an incorrect writing technique.
3. The authors state even 1 wt.% of impurity in ABS can cause unacceptable reductions in results however, this is usually the case for most polymers. I would suggest listing specific impurities in ABS processing or leaving it more general to most plastics.
4. I would argue high technology sector's hesitation to implement recycled compounds is due to the lack of repeatability from lot to lot with recycled polymers which would result in injury or warranty issues for the company, leading to money loss. This is opposed to just the materials' performance itself just decreasing the mechanical properties.

5. **The authors write that polymers and their properties all decrease as a result of aging however this is not true. If material crosslinks and branches as a result of degradation then viscosity and tensile strength increases. If the material is annealed, then the modulus and overall hardness increases. Please correct that statement on page 3 end of paragraph 2.**

-- Materials and Methods --

1. **Did the authors dry the PC and ABS/PC blends?**

1. **ABS may be hydrophobic but PC is reported to be broadline and other papers have reported drying PC before processing.**

2. **Do the authors have the exact formulations for the 2 industrial case studies?**

1. **The post-consumer parts can/be filled with a ton of additives to prevent aging which will offset the trend there were seen. As well, the date of production and or length of service will also have a significant impact on the properties of the post-consumer parts.**

3. **Are PC and ABS compatible with one another in blending operations?**

-- Results --

The results for this work are what would have been expected from this type of work. However, 2 major issues are present in this work.

1. **The material was seemingly "recycled" in an injection molding machine which is not an adequate method for studying this. It is not adequate because this type of recycling process (post-consumer (e.g. down cycling)) typically includes a twin screw extruder which imparts greater thermo-mechanical forces such as shear and heat compared to a single screw injection molding machine. In addition, the residence time in an extruder would be different when compared to an Injection molding machine. Also, if blending the recycled offsets into a virgin matrix via injection molding cause the results, in general, to be questioned as the mixing of the different constituents would be poor and not efficient as single screw set-ups are used to convey material from one end (feeding zone) to the other end (die). They are NOT to mix/blend like a twin screw set-up would.**

The authors need to justify this for this manuscript to be accepted.

2. **The tensile strength results are not statistically significant and with the lack of mention I would assume no ANOVA was performed on these results. However, looking at the means of the results, show that these results are highly likely to all be statistically insignificant (FIG 4, 5, 8, 9). This is not bad, necessarily, as it just means the material is more stable but the results discussion needs to reflect the no significance in tensile results.**

Please provide an ANOVA to prove your tensile results are significant.

The lack of tensile results may be a result of "recycling" within a single screw and not using a twin screw resulting in little chain scission.

3. **With the last point, the ABS/PC ref to after aging electronic, I would argue is not significant. Please check with ANOVA.**

4. **To prove chain scission, molecular weight analysis through whatever means (GPC, DLS, rheology) should be included.**

5. **The authors are constantly flipping between tensile strength and modulus. I assumed this is all tensile strength but please look through the entire work and fix it.**

6. **Please include the standard deviation in Table 3.**

7. **Include 100% cycle 1 in bar graphs. The reader should not have to work to compare your results.**

8. Was the supporting information file uploaded as well?

I could not locate it so please ensure you have uploaded it.

-- Conclusion --

No comment

-- Abstract --

Well written and concise - no other comment.

Is the background of the case's history and progression described in sufficient detail?

Partly

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Is the case presented with sufficient detail to be useful for teaching or other practitioners?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Polymeric recycling, processing/compounding of blends and composites as well as polymer characterization (advanced/standard).

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 22 Nov 2024

Denise GARCÍA MURIAS

--Introduction --

1. **I would suggest adding a line for the specific production/waste or collection rate for ABS and PC plastics to strengthen why these two materials should be of focus.**

ANSWER: A paragraph has been included in the next version of the article submitted, within the introduction section, highlighting the waste and collection rates of these polymers.

1. Polymer names are common nouns, and as such should not need to be capitalized, please finish on page 3 second paragraph. The capitalization may be just for the acronym but it is still an incorrect writing technique.

ANSWER: Thanks for the comments, polymers nouns have been fixed accordingly (mainly found in the introduction) in the next version submitted.

1. The authors state even 1 wt.% of impurity in ABS can cause unacceptable reductions in results however, this is usually the case for most polymers. I would suggest listing specific impurities in ABS processing or leaving it more general to most plastics.

ANSWER: Thanks for the valuable suggestion. The reference was adjusted to show a more general view of the phenomena.

1. I would argue high technology sector's hesitation to implement recycled compounds is due to the lack of repeatability from lot to lot with recycled polymers which would result in injury or warranty issues for the company, leading to money loss. This is opposed to just the materials' performance itself just decreasing the mechanical properties.

ANSWER: Thanks for the suggestion, we introduced a comment highlighting this possible fact in the introduction.

1. **The authors write that polymers and their properties all decrease as a result of aging however this is not true. If material crosslinks and branches as a result of degradation then viscosity and tensile strength increases. If the material is annealed, then the modulus and overall hardness increases. Please correct that statement on page 3 end of paragraph 2.**

ANSWER: Thanks for the comment. We stated there are several factors that can affect the performance of the material at the EOL, ageing, impurities presence, reprocessing cycles and amount of recycled material. It does not mean they decrease; it means they "impact negatively" on the performance of the material where the modified properties resultant after they EOL could be probably not desired. -- Materials and Methods --

1. **Did the authors dry the PC and ABS/PC blends?**

1. **ABS may be hydrophobic but PC is reported to be broadline and other papers have reported drying PC before processing.**

ANSWER: Yes, the materials were dried before the injection procedure. Polymers were dried before injecting it with a WITTMANN DRYMAX E30 and their moisture was measured with a Brabender Moisture meter AQUATRAC® - 3E. This comment was included in the methods section.

1. **Do the authors have the exact formulations for the 2 industrial case studies?**

1. **The post-consumer parts can/be filled with a ton of additives to prevent aging which will offset the trend there were seen. As well, the date or production and or length of service will also have a significant impact on the properties of the post-consumer parts.**

ANSWER: Thanks for the suggestion. Unfortunately, the exact formulations cannot be disclosed as they are commercial products belonging to a private consortium in a European project.

1. Are PC and ABS compatible with one another in blending operations?

ANSWER: Thanks for the question. For this project, the PC/ABS was selected from the commercially available ones in the market. In this case, a (PC + ABS) Lupoy HR5007A White specially used for injection molding was chosen. -- Results --

The results for this work are what would have been expected from this type of work.

However, 2 major issues are present in this work.

1. **The material was seemingly "recycled" in an injection molding machine which is not an adequate method for studying this. It is not adequate because this type of recycling process (post-consumer (e.g. down cycling)) typically includes a twin screw extruder which imparts greater thermo-mechanical forces such as shear and heat compared to a single screw injection molding machine. In addition, the residence time in an extruder would be different when compared to an Injection molding machine.**

Also, if blending the recycled offsets into a virgin matrix via injection molding cause the results, in general, to be questioned as the mixing of the different constituents would be poor and not efficient as single screw set-ups are used to convey material from one end (feeding zone) to the other end (die). They are NOT to mix/blend like a twin-screw set-up would.

The authors need to justify this for this manuscript to be accepted.

ANSWER: Thanks for the question and explanation. We think that the reviewer is mostly right about his/her assumption. Our machine is an injection molding machine Engel Victory 350Tn. It consists of a single-screw injection molding machine. The procedure for testing the mechanical recycling effect was as follows, first, the material (recycled) was shredded into new small pieces and then mixed with virgin ones in a mixing machine. Then, they are injected again to manufacture new test samples. We used this procedure as it was the common one for the recycling industry, being our intention to be a real simulation of the loss of properties only during this step. Although by using an extruder machine the mixing would be better, we did not use an extruder machine as we believe that this could bring additional thermo-mechanical stress to the material, making the comparison to the virgin material even harder and not aligned within the aim of the project. We introduced comments in the method section including the mixing machine we were using to obtain the pellets for injection.

1. **The tensile strength results are not statistically significant and with the lack of mention I would assume no ANOVA was performed on these results. However, looking at the means of the results, show that these results are highly likely to all be statistically insignificant (FIG 4, 5, 8, 9). This is not bad, necessarily, as it just means the material is more stable but the results discussion needs to reflect the no significance in tensile results.**

Please provide an ANOVA to prove your tensile results are significant.

The lack of tensile results may be a result of "recycling" within a single screw and not using a twin screw resulting in little chain scission.

ANSWER: Thanks a lot for the suggestions. We performed ANOVA (one factor variance) in the results from figures 4,5,8 and 9. The data from Figure 4 showed that there is not a

significant variance on the results: ANÁLISIS DE VARIANZA *Origen de las variaciones*
Suma de cuadrados Grados de libertad Promedio de los cuadrados F Probabilidad Valor crítico
 para F Entre grupos 33449.55 3 11149.85 **2.906305 0.0668551 3.238872** Dentro de los
 grupos 61382.96 16 3836.435 Total 94832.51 19 The data from Figure 5
 showed that there is a significant variance on the results: ANÁLISIS DE VARIANZA
Origen de las variaciones Suma de cuadrados Grados de libertad Promedio de los cuadrados F
Probabilidad Valor crítico para F Entre grupos 439245.7 3 146415.2 **57.84654 8.28E-09**
3.238872 Dentro de los grupos 40497.56 16 2531.098 Total 479743.3 19 For
 Figure 8, results showed that there is not a significant variance: ANÁLISIS DE VARIANZA
Origen de las variaciones Suma de cuadrados Grados de libertad Promedio de los cuadrados F
Probabilidad Valor crítico para F Entre grupos 50705.5281 2 25352.7641 **1.73130012**
0.21847025 3.88529383 Dentro de los grupos 175725.263 12 14643.7719 Total
 226430.791 14 For Figure 8, results showed that there is not a significant variance:
 ANÁLISIS DE VARIANZA *Origen de las variaciones Suma de cuadrados Grados de libertad*
Promedio de los cuadrados F Probabilidad Valor crítico para F Entre grupos 1082.1056 2
 541.0528 0.03631791 0.96443924 3.88529383 Dentro de los grupos 178772.201 12
 14897.6834 Total 179854.307 14 Based on this, a comment was included in
 the discussion showing this results and a sum-up table was included in the supporting
 information along with a brief discussion.

1. **With the last point, the ABS/PC ref to after aging electronic, I would argue is not significant. Please check with ANOVA.**

ANSWER: Thanks for the suggestion. We checked by analysis of variance (ANOVA) at 95% confidence level the results and found that whereas ABS showed important differences, ABS/PC performed in a more resilient way. ANÁLISIS DE VARIANZA-ABS tensile test
Origen de las variaciones Suma de cuadrados Grados de libertad Promedio de los cuadrados F
Probabilidad Valor crítico para F Entre grupos 293697.4541 1 293697.454 20.7431082
 0.00054073 4.66719273 Dentro de los grupos 184064.3587 13 14158.7968 Total
 477761.8128 14 ANÁLISIS DE VARIANZA-ABS/PC tensile test *Origen de las*
variaciones Suma de cuadrados Grados de libertad Promedio de los cuadrados F Probabilidad
Valor crítico para F Entre grupos 40924.3494 1 40924.3494 2.3400345 0.15004974
 4.66719273 Dentro de los grupos 227354.144 13 17488.7803 Total 268278.494 14

As you can check above, the results for ABS are far more divergent than for ABS/PC. A comment was included in the "Effect of the ageing on the mechanical properties of the material" results part.

1. **To prove chain scission, molecular weight analysis through whatever means (GPC, DLS, rheology) should be included.**

ANSWER: Thanks for the suggestion. We agree that these tests could help to obtain better insights into the results. Unfortunately, these tests were not included into project proposal, and we do not have such techniques in our facilities portfolio.

1. **The authors are constantly flipping between tensile strength and modulus. I assumed this is all tensile strength but please look through the entire work and fix it.**

ANSWER: Thanks for pointing out this fact. We found that it is better to harmonize everything on "tensile modulus" and "impact resistance". Following this, a revision was made through all the document and all images have been modified accordingly. **Please include the standard deviation in Table 3.**

ANSWER: Thanks for the suggestion. Table 3 was modified to include the standard

deviation.

1. **Include 100% cycle 1 in bar graphs. The reader should not have to work to compare your results.**

ANSWER: Thanks for the valuable suggestion, Figures from 4 to 7 has been modified according to your comments.

1. Was the supporting information file uploaded as well?

I could not locate it so please ensure you have uploaded it.

ANSWER: Yes, supporting information document was also included in the next version submitted. -- Conclusion --

No comment

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 10 June 2024

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.18250.r40703>

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Macaulay Mfon Owen

Universiti Tenaga Nasional, Kajang, Selangor, Malaysia

Reviewer's comments/ Reports:

The article titled "Impact of recyclability on the mechanical properties of coated plastic materials for the automotive and electronic sectors" have been reviewed.

The research focuses on the study of the mechanical properties (tensile and impact strength) of Acrylonitrile-Butadiene-Styrene (ABS) and its blends with Polycarbonate (ABS/PC) including recycled and painted material, to determine the impact of ageing, reprocessing cycles, and coating impurities on the final properties of the recycled polymer.

The research is an interesting study, and well written within the scope. However, a significant revision is needed to further improve on the quality of the manuscript.

The research novelty must be clearly emphasized with strong justifications in the introduction and literature sections, as there are lot of work already done on ABS, blends of ABS/PC and their recyclability.

Research title:

I am of the opinion that the title should be reviewed as "***Impact of recyclability on the tensile and Impact properties of coated plastic materials for the automotive and electronic sectors***"

Because only tensile and impact tests were done.

Methods:

State the processing temperature, pressure and time used.

How did you determine the processing temperature used for the injection moulding of the recycled ABS, and ABS/PC?.

Mechanical recycling process:

Mention the equipment used for the shredding process.

Coating Impurities:

Explain the coating impurities and give some examples.

List out the parameters of the five-cycle reprocessing process used.

Characterizations and Testing

Mechanical tests; Why did you not conduct other mechanical tests such as compressive, flexural, hardness, etc.,

Thermal Analysis;

There are no any thermal analysis mentioned in your work. Why did you not conduct DSC and TGA?

Microstructural Analysis;

Why didn't you carry out Scanning Electron Microscope SEM?

Is the background of the case's history and progression described in sufficient detail?

Yes

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Partly

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Yes

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

No

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Is the case presented with sufficient detail to be useful for teaching or other practitioners?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Engineering thermoplastic polymer processing, Polymer composites, Fiber reinforced composites, Materials processing, characterization and testing, Textiles, Fibers, wovens and Nonwovens, Chemical treatments,

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have

significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 22 Nov 2024

Denise GARCÍA MURIAS

Reviewer's comments/ Reports + Replies from authors in blue below:

The article titled "Impact of recyclability on the mechanical properties of coated plastic materials for the automotive and electronic sectors" have been reviewed. The research focuses on the study of the mechanical properties (tensile and impact strength) of Acrylonitrile-Butadiene-Styrene (ABS) and its blends with Polycarbonate (ABS/PC) including recycled and painted material, to determine the impact of ageing, reprocessing cycles, and coating impurities on the final properties of the recycled polymer.

The research is an interesting study, and well written within the scope. However, a significant revision is needed to further improve on the quality of the manuscript.

The research novelty must be clearly emphasized with strong justifications in the introduction and literature sections, as there are lot of work already done on ABS, blends of ABS/PC and their recyclability. Within the next version of the article submitted today, a comment was included in the introduction highlighting the differentiation between this study as a proof of closed working and the common research studies.

- **Suggestion 1: Research title:**

I am of the opinion that the title should be reviewed as "Impact of recyclability on the tensile and Impact properties of coated plastic materials for the automotive and electronic sectors" Because only tensile and impact tests were done.

Answer 1:

Thanks for the suggestion, we changed the title accordingly in the next version submitted as we believe it matches better the content.

- **Suggestion 2: Methods:**

State the processing temperature, pressure and time used. How did you determine the processing temperature used for the injection moulding of the recycled ABS, and ABS/PC?. **Answer 2:**

Thanks for the valuable suggestion. The processing temperatures were determined according to the TDS of the selected polymers:

- For ABS, a temperature of 220-240 °C for the plastificator part and 70 °C for the mold. Pressure was 65-70/25-30/7 Kg/cm² (injection/post-pressure/counterpressure). The total time for injection (including all steps) was around 60 s.
- For ABS/PC, a temperature of 240-270 °C for the plastificator part and 70 °C for the mold. The injection machine conditions were 60-65/20-25/7 Kg/cm² (injection/post-pressure/counterpressure). The total time for injection (including all steps) was around 50 s.

A comment stating this parameters are now included in the methods section.

- **Suggestion 3: Mechanical recycling process:**

Mention the equipment used for the shredding process.

Answer 3: Thanks for the comment. The granulator machine used was a WITTMANN G-MAX 23. This was included in the draft in in the methods section.

- **Suggestion 4: Coating Impurities:**

Explain the coating impurities and give some examples.

List out the parameters of the five-cycle reprocessing process used.

Answer 4: Thanks for the suggestion and focus on injection parameters. We believe it could improve our article. The coating impurities were made mostly of paint residues. According to the TDS for the coatings, these are made of an acrylic-based coating. A comment highlighting this was included in page 7. The conditions for the five cycles were similar as the ones stated before in **Answer 2**. Temperatures were decreased a bit whereas slightly pressures were augmented to increase fluidity and compactness of the resulting testing pieces.

Characterizations and Testing

- **Suggestion 5: Mechanical tests:**

Why did you not conduct other mechanical tests such as compressive, flexural, hardness, etc.,

Answer 5: Thanks for the tests suggestions. Other mechanical tests were not included as they were not part of the project nor included into the assigned budget. Tensile and impact were chosen as the ones with higher impact and representativity for the study. Although we believe that if the study was more general with regard to the mechanical properties, the mentioned tests could be a good addition.

- **Suggestion 6: Thermal Analysis:**

There are no thermal analysis mentioned in your work. Why did you not conduct DSC and TGA?

Answer 6: Thanks for the suggestions. We believe that these techniques could bring higher insights about the degradation of the polymeric chains due to thermomechanical stress. However, in a similar way as the last suggestion, DSC and TGA were not included in the project, and it is very hard to perform them now as they are out of the assigned budget or tasks included into our work packages. Nonetheless, the objective of the article is to study the impact of recyclability on the mechanical properties, although we are aware of the relation with thermal processes. As it could be necessary to include newer tests on the study, some comments about the needs of future tests for SEM were included into the draft in page 12.

- **Suggestion 7: Microstructural Analysis:**

Why didn't you carry out Scanning Electron Microscope SEM?

Answer 7: Thanks for the valuable suggestions. SEM is a very interesting technique to include that could give us deep knowledge about the microstructure of the polymers. Unfortunately, we do not have such technique into our facilities and this test was not included as part of the budget for the related European project. As there was a focus on newer tests to include more information than the current one, some comments about the needs of future tests for SEM were included into the draft in page 13.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.